

Novel Indolyl Formazans as Potent Anticonvulsant and MAO Inhibitors

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4-[4,5-Dihydro-4-[(2-substituted-1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]-2-methyl/phenyl-5-oxo-1*H*-imidazol-1-yl]benzoic acid, [(substituted-phenyl)methylene]hydrazides (5a-1) were prepared by refluxing different substituted aryl aldehydes with 4-[4,5-dihydro-5-oxo-2-methyl/phenyl-4-[(2-substituted-1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]-1*H*-imidazol-1-yl]benzoic acid hydrazides (4a-d) in ethanol containing few drops of glacial acetic acid. The hydrazides (4a-d) in turn have been obtained by refluxing the corresponding esters (3a-d) with hydrazine hydrate. Novel cyclic formazans were synthesised by azotype coupling of 5a-1 with arene diazonium chlorides. The compounds were screened for their anticonvulsant and monoamine oxidase inhibitory activities and some of them exhibited promising results.

THE wide-spread occurrence of the indole nucleus among both natural and synthetic psychoactive agents and investigation of 5-hydroxytryptamine as MAO (monoamine oxidase) inhibitor¹ have initiated a great promise in the investigations of a number of analogue compounds with potent CNS activities. Furthermore, various formazans possess anticonvulsant and MAO inhibitory activities² besides having other biological properties^{3,4}. In view of these potentialities of the indole derivatives, several new indolylformazans were synthesised in an attempt to obtain compounds with more pronounced anticonvulsant activity and minimum toxicity.

2-Methyl/phenyl-4-[(2-substituted-1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]-5-(4*H*)oxazolone (2) on condensation with methyl 4-aminobenzoate yield methyl 4-[4,5-dihydro-2-methyl/phenyl-5-oxo-4-[(2-substituted-1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]-1*H*-imidazol-1-yl]benzoate (3) which on reaction with hydrazine hydrate followed by aryl aldehydes yield 4-[4,5-dihydro-4-[(2-substituted-1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]-2-methyl/phenyl-5-oxo-1*H*-imidazol-1-yl]benzoic acid, [(substituted-phenyl)methylene]hydrazide (5a-1). The hydrazones (5) were subsequently converted into the formazans (6za) by substitution of the arylidene protons with arylidiazonium group (Scheme 1). A characteristic ir band in support of structure 6 was observed at 1 580 cm⁻¹ (N=N).

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Purity of compounds was checked by tlc on silica gel G. Ir spectra (KBr) were taken on a Perkin-Elmer 157 Infracord spectrophotometer, pmr spectra (CDCl₃) on a Varian A 60D spectrometer using TMS as an

internal standard and mass spectra on a JMSD 300 instrument fitted with JMS 2000 data system at 70 eV.

2-Substituted-indol-3-aldehyde⁵ (1) and 2-methyl/phenyl-4-[(2-substituted-1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]-5(4*H*)-oxazolones⁶ (2) were synthesised by following the reported methods.

*Methyl-4-[4,5-dihydro-2-methyl/phenyl-5-oxo-4-[(2-substituted-1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]-1*H*-imidazol-1-yl]benzoates (3a-d)*: An equimolar mixture of compound 1 and methyl 4-aminobenzoate was heated in an oil-bath at 140° for 10-20 min. The resulting jelly-like mass was crystallised from benzene/petroleum ether: methyl 4-[4,5-dihydro-4-(1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]-2-methyl-5-oxo-1*H*-imidazol-1-yl]benzoate (3a; 80%), m.p. 118° (Found: N, 11.67. C₂₁H₁₇N₃O₃ requires: N, 11.69%); methyl 4-[4,5-dihydro-4-(1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]-5-oxo-2-phenyl-1*H*-imidazol-1-yl]benzoate (3b; 78%), m.p. 73° (Found: N, 9.95. C₂₀H₁₆N₃O₃ requires: N, 9.96%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 675 (C=O), 1 640 (C=N) and 3 035 cm⁻¹ (aromatic CH); methyl 4-[4,5-dihydro-2-methyl-5-oxo-4-[(2-phenyl-1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]-1*H*-imidazol-1-yl]benzoate (3c; 80%), m.p. 87° (Found: N, 9.64. C₂₇H₂₁N₃O₃ requires: N, 9.65%); methyl 4-[4,5-dihydro-5-oxo-2-phenyl-4-[(2-phenyl-1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]-1*H*-imidazol-1-yl]benzoate (3d; 75%), m.p. 110° (Found: N, 8.44. C₃₂H₂₅N₃O₃ requires: N, 8.45%).

4 [4,5-Dihydro-5-oxo-2-methyl/phenyl-4-[(2-substituted-1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]-1*H*-imidazol-1-yl]benzoic acid hydrazides (4a-d): Compounds 3a-d (40 g) were refluxed with hydrazine hydrate (0.015 mol; 99%) in ethanol for 8 h to yield the products: 4-[4,5-dihydro-4-(1*H*-indol-3-yl)methylene]-2-methyl-5-oxo-1*H*-imidazol-1-yl]benzoic acid hydrazide

Scheme 1

(4a; 75%); m.p. 156° (Found: N, 19.47. $C_{29}H_{17}N_5O_3$ requires: N, 19.49%); 4-[4,5-dihydro-4-(1H-indol-3-ylmethylene)-5-oxo-2-phenyl-1H-imidazol-1-yl]benzoic acid hydrazide (4b; 78%), m.p. 162° (Found: N, 16.61. $C_{25}H_{19}N_5O_3$ requires: N, 16.62%); ν_{max} (KBr) 1 670 (C=O), 1 640 (C=N), 1 720 (CONH), 3 350 (NH) and 3 030 cm^{-1} (aromatic CH); 4-[4,5-dihydro-2-methyl-5-oxo-4-[(2-phenyl-1H-indol-3-yl)methylene]-1H-imidazol-1-yl]benzoic acid hydrazide (4c; 75%), m.p. 117° (Found: N, 16.08. $C_{26}H_{21}N_5O_3$ requires: N, 16.09%); 4-[4,5-dihydro-5-oxo-2-phenyl-4-[(2-phenyl-1H-indol-3-yl)methylene]-1H-imidazol-1-yl]ben-

zoic acid hydrazide (4d; 75%), m.p. 152° (Found: N, 14.08. $C_{31}H_{25}N_5O_3$ requires: N, 14.08%).

4-[4,5-Dihydro-4-[(2-substituted-1H-indol-3-yl-methylene)-2-methyl]phenyl-5-oxo-1H-imidazol-1-yl]-benzoic acid, [(substituted-phenyl)methylene]hydrazide (5a-1): A mixture of 4a-d (0.01 mol) and different substituted aryl aldehydes (0.01 mol) in ethanol containing few drops of glacial acetic acid was refluxed for 5 h and the excess solvent was then removed by distillation. The solid obtained on cooling was filtered, washed and recrystallised from ethanol, ν_{max} (KBr) 1 680 (C=O), 1 645 (C=N), 1 710 (CONH), 3 010 (N=CH), 3 400 (NH), 3 030 (ArH) and 2 920 cm^{-1} (aliphatic CH); δ (CDCl₃) 8.0 (1H, s, N=CH), 8.8 (s, NH indole), 6.3 (1H, s, CH), 6.7-7.8 (18H, m, ArH) Characterisation data of compounds are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1 - PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 5a-1*

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
5a	H	CH ₃	H	238	75	C ₂₇ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₃
5b	H	CH ₃	2-OH	258	62	C ₂₇ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄
5c	H	CH ₃	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OCH ₃	143	68	C ₂₉ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₄
5d	H	C ₆ H ₅	H	154	70	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₃
5e	H	C ₆ H ₅	2-OH	135	72	C ₂₈ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄
5f	H	C ₆ H ₅	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OCH ₃	122	65	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₄
5g	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	H	110	60	C ₂₈ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₃
5h	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	2-OH	104	72	C ₂₈ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₄
5i	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OCH ₃	114	69	C ₃₀ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₄
5j	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	H	137	71	C ₂₉ H ₂₁ N ₅ O ₃
5k	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	2-OH	201	66	C ₂₉ H ₁₉ N ₅ O ₄
5l	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OCH ₃	95	70	C ₃₁ H ₂₃ N ₅ O ₄

*All compounds gave satisfactory N analysis.

4-[4,5-Dihydro-4-[(2-substituted-1H-indol-3-yl-methylene)-2-methyl]phenyl-5-oxo-1H-imidazol-1-yl]-benzoic acid [(substituted-phenyl)-[(substituted-phenyl)azo]methylene]hydrazide (6a-za): The appropriate amine (0.02 mol) in glacial acetic acid (2 ml) and HCl (1.5 ml) were diazotised with sodium nitrite (0.2 g in 2 ml water) at 0-5°. The resulting diazonium chloride solution was then added with stirring to the solution of 4 (0.01 mol) in cold pyridine. The reaction mixture was left overnight at ambient temperature. It was then poured into ice-cold water (250 ml) with continuous stirring when a dark coloured solid separated out. It was filtered, washed repeatedly with water and recrystallised from methanol/water, ν_{max} (KBr) 3 030 (aromatic CH), 1 580 (N=N), 1 600 (C=N) and 2 950 cm^{-1} (CH₂); m/z 565 (M^+).

Similarly, other formazan derivatives were synthesised (Table 2).

Biological activity: The substituted indolyl formazans were tested *in vitro* for their monoamine oxidase inhibitory activity and *in vivo* for their anticonvulsant and analgesic activity in albino mice.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 6a—za*

Compd. no.	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃	R ₄	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
6a	H	CH ₃	H	2-CH ₃	296	65	C ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₇ O ₃
b	H	CH ₃	H	4-Cl	168	60	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ N ₇ O ₃ Cl
c	H	CH ₃	2-OH	2-CH ₃	175	52	C ₂₄ H ₂₇ N ₇ O ₄
d	H	CH ₃	2-OH	4-Cl	116	64	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ N ₇ O ₃ Cl
e	H	CH ₃	2-OH	3-Cl	142	67	C ₂₃ H ₂₄ N ₇ O ₃ Cl
f	H	CH ₃	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OCH ₃	2-CH ₃	325	54	C ₂₆ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₄
g	H	CH ₃	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OCH ₃	4-Cl	152	48	C ₂₅ H ₂₈ N ₇ O ₄ Cl
h	H	C ₆ H ₅	H	2-CH ₃	204	61	C ₂₉ H ₂₉ N ₇ O ₃
i	H	C ₆ H ₅	H	4-Cl	180	58	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ N ₇ O ₃ Cl
j	H	C ₆ H ₅	2-OH	2-CH ₃	195	53	C ₂₉ H ₂₈ N ₇ O ₄
k	H	C ₆ H ₅	2-OH	4-Cl	172	50	C ₂₈ H ₂₈ N ₇ O ₃ Cl
l	H	C ₆ H ₅	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OCH ₃	2-CH ₃	215	60	C ₃₁ H ₃₁ N ₇ O ₄
m	H	C ₆ H ₅	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OCH ₃	4-Cl	175	62	C ₃₀ H ₃₀ N ₇ O ₄ Cl
n	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	H	2-CH ₃	318	59	C ₄₀ H ₃₁ N ₇ O ₃
o	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	H	4-Cl	108	65	C ₃₉ H ₃₀ N ₇ O ₃ Cl
p	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	2-OH	2-CH ₃	172	47	C ₄₀ H ₃₁ N ₇ O ₄
q	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	2-OH	4-Cl	190	62	C ₃₉ H ₃₀ N ₇ O ₃ Cl
r	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OCH ₃	2-CH ₃	167	57	C ₄₁ H ₃₅ N ₇ O ₄
s	C ₆ H ₅	CH ₃	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OCH ₃	4-Cl	119	54	C ₄₀ H ₃₀ N ₇ O ₄ Cl
t	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	H	2-CH ₃	235	68	C ₄₄ H ₃₃ N ₇ O ₃
u	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	H	4-Cl	102	56	C ₄₃ H ₃₀ N ₇ O ₃ Cl
v	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	2-OH	2-CH ₃	180	60	C ₄₄ H ₃₃ N ₇ O ₄
w	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	2-OH	4-Cl	138	52	C ₄₃ H ₃₀ N ₇ O ₃ Cl
x	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	2-OH	3-NO ₂	118	64	C ₄₄ H ₃₀ N ₇ O ₄
y	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OCH ₃	2-CH ₃	201	63	C ₄₇ H ₃₇ N ₇ O ₄
z	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OCH ₃	4-Cl	125	67	C ₄₆ H ₃₄ N ₇ O ₄ Cl
za	C ₆ H ₅	C ₆ H ₅	3-OCH ₃ , 4-OCH ₃	3-NO ₂	101	54	C ₄₆ H ₃₆ N ₇ O ₆

*All compounds showed satisfactory N analysis.

In vitro biochemical studies: Adult albino rats (100–150 g) were killed by decapitation. The brain was quickly removed and homogenised in 0.25 M sucrose using a Potter-Elvehjem homogeniser. The contents were chilled throughout the operation. The final volume of homogenate was 10% (w/v) of fresh tissue. Various enzyme inhibitory activities were determined using this preparation as a source of enzyme. For the determination of inhibitory activities, the compounds were dissolved in propylene glycol which did not have any inhibitory effect against the enzyme activities at the concentration used in the assay system. A suitable aliquot of the test solution was added so that the desired concentration in the final volume of reaction was obtained. The percent inhibition was calculated from the decrease in optical density.

In vitro determination of MAO activity: The spectrophotofluorometric method⁷ was used for the determination of monoamine oxidase activity of the rat brain homogenate using kynuramine as substrate. The 4-hydroxyquinoline formed during oxidative deamination of kynuramine was measured fluorometrically in an Aminco-Bowman spectrophotofluorometer using activating light of 355 nm and measuring fluorescence at 380 nm. The compounds were used at the final concentration of 1×10^{-4} M.

In vivo pharmacological studies: Anticonvulsant activity⁸ was determined against pentylenetetrazol

induced convulsions in albino mice of either sex (25–30 g). All the compounds were suspended in 5% gum acacia and were injected intraperitoneally in a group of 10 animals at a dose of 100 mg/kg. The mice were injected with pentylenetetrazol (80 mg/kg subcutaneously) 4 h after the administration of compounds. The animals were observed for 60 min for the occurrence of seizure. An episode of clonic spasm persisting for at least 5 s was considered a threshold convulsion. Animal not exhibiting even a threshold convulsion during 60 minutes were considered protected. The number of animals protected in each group were recorded and anticonvulsant activity was represented as percent protection.

Analgesic activity. Mouse tail pinch method: Morphine-like analgesic activity⁹ was tested by the mouse tail pinch method. Compounds were injected intraperitoneally in 5% aqueous suspension of gum acacia at a dose of 100 mg/kg. Four hours after the administration of compounds, an artery clip with branches enclosed in a thin rubber tube was applied to the root of the tail of a mouse for 30 s. The animals made continuous attempts to remove the noxious stimulus by biting the clips. The insensitivity to the noxious stimulus was taken as the positive response and the results were expressed as percentage of mice showing analgesic activity. Morphine hydrochloride was used as a reference standard for comparing the effective analgesic property of these compounds.

TABLE 3 - ANTICONVULSANT AND ENZYME INHIBITORY ACTIVITIES OF COMPOUNDS 6a - za

Compd. no.	Anticonvulsant activity % protection (100 mg/kg i.p.)	Analgesic activity (%) (100 mg/kg i.p.)	MAO inhibition (%)* at $\times 10^{-4}$ M	ALD ₅₀ mg/kg i.p.
6a	60	20	10.1	500
b	80	20	15.8	1 000
c	100	20	36.3	1 200
d	80	40	40.6	1 000
e	70	20	51.4	500
f	90	40	52.2	800
g	80	40	50.2	600
h	80	60	75.6	1 000
i	60	60	12.8	800
j	20	80	10.6	500
k	20	60	11.4	500
l	40	10	23.3	800
m	40	40	25.9	600
n	80	40	88.7	1 000
o	40	60	72.3	600
p	80	80	13.3	600
q	70	10	36.5	800
r	100	10	13.2	1 200
s	80	40	17.8	1 000
t	80	60	20.8	1 000
u	60	40	69.3	800
v	80	40	25.3	1 000
w	80	80	44.5	600
x	60	40	23.3	800
y	80	30	15.9	1 000
z	80	40	45.5	1 000
za	90	40	53.4	1 200
Control	0	0	-	-
Phenobarb (15 mg/kg i.p.)	40	-	-	-
Morphine HCl (5 mg/kg i.p.)	-	100	-	-
Phenelzine (1×10^{-5} M)	-	-	78.0	-

*Each experiment was done in duplicate and the figure indicates mean values of two separate experiments.

Toxicity study: Approximate lethal doses (ALD₅₀)¹⁰ of the compounds were determined in albino mice. The animals were divided into group of 4 each and were fasted for 18 h prior to the drug administration. The compounds were given in doses of 500, 600, 800, 1000 and 1200 mg/kg intraperitoneally and 24 h mortality was recorded.

Results and Discussion

The ability of indolyl formazans to inhibit rat brain monoamine oxidase at final concentration of 1×10^{-4} M has been recorded in Table 3. Maximum MAO inhibition was afforded by compound 6n having electron-releasing CH₃ substituents as R₂ and R₄ when position-2 of the indole as R₁ was occupied by phenyl ring as compared to compound 1 in which indole ring was unsubstituted exhibited minimum enzyme inhibitory activity of 10.1% among the derivatives.

Further, when the variation was made at different positions in the phenyl ring as R₃ it was observed that compounds having 2-hydroxy or 3,4-dimethoxy substituents as R₃ exhibited moderate MAO inhibitory activity in which posi-

tion-2 of the imidazolinone ring as R₃ was occupied by methyl group (*cf.* compounds 6c-g) as compared to derivatives in which phenyl ring as R₃ was unsubstituted (*cf.* compounds 6a,b). Moreover, derivatives in which position-2 of the imidazolinone ring as R₂ was occupied by phenyl group exhibited low degree of inhibition of enzyme monoamine oxidase (*cf.* compounds 6i-m) except compound 6h which produced significant enzyme inhibition (76.6%) having *ortho*-methyl substituent as R₄ and R₃ remains unsubstituted.

As evident from Table 3, these compounds afforded protection from 20-100% against pentylenetetrazol induced seizures in albino mice. Maximum protection was afforded by compounds 6c and 6r having electron-releasing methyl substituents at position-2 of the phenyl ring as R₂ and R₄ while compounds 6j and k containing hydroxy substituents at position-2 of the phenyl ring as R₃ showed minimum protective ability of 20%. It was observed that presence of methyl group at position-2 of the imidazolinone ring is proved beneficial for the activity in which indole ring was unsubstituted as these derivatives produced signifi-

cant protection against seizures (*cf.* compound 6a–g). However, substantial decrease in activity was observed when position-2 of the imidazolinone ring was occupied by phenyl group (*cf.* compounds 6h–m). Further, presence of methyl group at position-2 of the phenyl ring in 3,4-dimethoxy substituted derivatives exhibited significant anticonvulsant activity (*cf.* compounds f, l, q and y) whereas a comparative decrease in protective ability was shown when 4-chloro substituent was introduced in the phenyl ring as R₄ (*cf.* compounds 6g, m, s and z). The two active derivatives (6c and 6r) having 100% protection were found to be the most active compounds of the series and were further evaluated at lower doses for their ED₅₀ values. Derivatives 6c and 6r were found to have an ED₅₀ values of 74.99 and 63.10 mg/kg i.p. (Table 4). These derivatives also exhibited high ALD₅₀ values thereby indicating their relatively high therapeutic margin.

TABLE 4—DETAILED ANTICONVULSANT ACTIVITY AND ED₅₀ OF COMPOUNDS 6c AND 6r

Compd. no.	Dose mg/kg i.p.	Anticonvulsant activity % protection	ED ₅₀ mg/kg i.p.
6c	50	30	74.99
	75	50	
	100	100	
6r	50	40	63.10
	75	70	
	100	100	

The analgesic activity exhibited by these compounds ranged from 10 to 80%. Compounds having hydroxy substituent at position-2 of the phenyl ring as R₃ was the most potent and capable of producing analgesia in 80% mice (*cf.* compounds 10, 16 and 24). Introduction of 4-chloro group in 3,4-dimethoxy substituted compounds is more sensitive to analgesic activity (*cf.* compounds 13, 19 and 26) as compared to the derivatives in which

methyl group was present at position 2 of the phenyl ring as R₄ (*cf.* compounds 12, 18 and 25) except compounds 6 and 7 in which 40% analgesic effect was observed.

The ALD₅₀ values (24 h) of these substituted formazans were found to be in the range 500–1200 mg/kg intraperitoneal in albino mice indicating their low toxicity and high therapeutic margin.

In the present study, the degree of protection afforded by all these compounds against pentylenetetrazol induced seizures could not show any parallelism with their *in vitro* monoamine oxidase inhibitory properties. These results provide further support to the earlier observation¹¹ that MAO inhibition is not fully concerned with the mechanism of action of the anticonvulsant activity of such MAO inhibitors.

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References

1. A. CARFETTI, *Prog. Drug Res.*, 1960, 2, 227.
2. G. SATHI, V. R. GUJRATI, C. NATH, J. C. AGARWAL, K. P. BHARGAVA and K. SHANKER, *Arzneim Forsch*, 1983, 33, 1218.
3. R. KALSI, K. PANDE, T. N. BHALLA, S. S. PARMAR and J. P. BARTH WAL, *Pharmacology*, 1988, 37, 218.
4. V. K. SRIVASTAVA, G. PALIT and K. SHANKER, *Indian Drugs*, 1987, 24, 325.
5. S. SWAMINATHAN and S. RANGANATHAN, *Chem. Ind.*, 1974, 53, 1974.
6. A. DHASMANA, J. P. BARTH WAL, A. K. SAXENA, T. K. GUPTA and G. P. GUPTA, *Indian J. Pharm Sci.*, 1981, 43, 94.
7. M. KRAJL, *Biochem. Pharmacol.*, 1965, 14, 1684.
8. S. S. PARMAR, B. R. PANDE, C. DWIVEDI and R. D. HARBINSON, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1974, 63, 1152.
9. C. BIANCHI, J. CHENI and FRANIES, *Br. J. Pharmacol. Chemother.*, 1959, 9, 280.
10. C. C. SMITH, *J. Pharmacol. Exp. Ther.*, 1950, 100, 408.
11. S. S. PARMAR, A. K. GUPTA, H. H. SINGH and T. K. GUPTA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1972, 15, 99.